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T (brachyury) induction in TNBC.

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The relative lack of requirement for hormone and ERBB growth factor signaling in TNBC suggests the existence of additional nuclear factors functioning in transformation during the development of triple negative breast cancer compared to the hormone receptor positive luminal A and luminal B subtypes. We used a novel quantitative approach to identify nuclear factors important for triple negative breast cancer development in humans. We identified the mesoderm specification factor T (also known as brachyury) as a likely required factor for oncogenesis to triple negative breast cancer in humans. The requirement for T in breast cancer development appears specific to hormone receptor negative (triple negative) disease. The data describe a developmental trajectory alluding to continued selection pressure across time that drives development and selection of stable lineages in the primary tumor (subtype).